

Social

A STUDY ABOUT STATUS OF SOCIAL JUSTICE IN INDIA

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Abstract

In the Indian context, the constitution makes envisaged a concept of social justice which involves the establishment of an egalitarian, social order where there was no discrimination among individuals on the basis of caste, religion, race, sex or place of birth. Goal of political, socio and economic democracy have been sought to be implemented through certain political and socio economic rights. These conditions were to be established by adopting a socio economic model of development through a policy of socialism. In present study year wise variation with respect to element of social justice is presented.

Keywords: Social Justice; India; Economic Rights.

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1. Introduction

The Indian constitution have provided necessary safeguards by certain provisions which make positive discrimination in favor of the weaker and disadvantaged sections of the society so that they could be able to avail the same opportunities as being availed by well off sections of the society.

The concept of social justice emerged out of a process of evolution of social norms, order, law and morality. It laid emphasis upon the just action and creates intervention in the society by enforcing the rules and regulations based on the principles in accordance with social equality. Social justice ensures liberty, equality and maintains their individual rights in the society. In other words, securing the highest possible development of the capabilities of all members of the society may be called social justice. In modern liberal philosophy "justice" is defined in terms of rights not as duties. Thus the notion of social justice requires the equal distribution of economic goods and opportunities. Social justice means availability of equal social opportunities for the full development of human personality to all the people in the society, without any

discrimination on the ground of caste, sex or race etc. Therefore, the notion of social justice is associated with social equality and individual rights.

It has to be said that though initially cast played a positive and liberating role for the socially disadvantaged sections of the society, but over the last decade cast has become an instrument of politicization. It has to be accepted that we should start pondering about moving towards another system of affirmative motion which is free of reservation of any type. We should move towards a system where in enough facilities would provide to weaker sections. Probably it would be proper to decide upon a time limit beyond which the facilities of reservation would not be extended. The challenges are to establish social justice so that disadvantaged sections may enjoy equal status in socio cultural sphere.

2. Objective of Study

To find status of elements of social justice year wise

3. Hypothesis

There is no difference in various dimensions of social justice year wise.

4. Methodology

Survey method is followed to find status of social justice in India. Social justice dimensions as human rights awareness, child labor, women empowerment, legal rights awareness, crime control are taken for study. Data is collected from govt. offices, social work places, news channels, Factories, newspapers, websites and magazines etc. Collected data is tabulated and year wise comparatively analyzed.

5. Finding & Analysis

Table 1: Status of Social Justice in last 5 years

Year	Human Rights Awareness %	Child Labor %	Women Empowerment %	Legal Rights Awareness %	Crime Control %
2011-12	45	9	13	23	3
2012-13	52.3	8.75	14.3	26	4.1
2013-14	57.5	8.3	16.1	29.3	4.7
2014-15	61.3	7.1	17.3	30.1	5.5
2015-16	64.4	6.5	18.1	32.3	6.3

Chart 1: Status of Social Justice in last 5 years

Data indicates that day by day human rights awareness is increasing, child labor % is decreasing, and parents are becoming aware about child's right. Women empowerment % is increasing with the advancement in communication technology and legal right awareness also increasing rapidly. Increasing rate of crime control shows efforts of administration to make developed society. Thus hypothesis, there is no difference in various dimensions of social justice year wise is rejected.

6. Conclusion

For a developed society, social justice is primary need. To make society strong and more powerful, empowerment of women, prosperity of poor, job for all are requirements. Though various initiatives have been taken by the government to achieve the target even though some of the targets are far from to achieve and still comprehensive programs and policies are required to achieve these targets.

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